

Lockdown fatigue, personal resilience and coping appraisal of faculty in a state university

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ABSTRACT

Many countries' lockdown measures have been effective in halting the spread of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, but there is rising worry about their negative effects on overall health and well-being, particularly among lecturer in the academe. This study aimed to assess the lockdown fatigue, personal resilience and coping appraisal involving 100 lecturers in Quirino State University-Diffun Campus. Four-likert scale questionnaires were adapted and used to gather data including the lockdown fatigue scale (LFS), brief resilience scale (BRS), and coping appraisal. Findings reveal that majority of the respondents are female, 31-40 years old, married, with an on-going Master's Degree, with a permanent position in the university. The most prominent symptoms of fatigue, according to the respondents in this study, were worry, sadness, depression, tiredness or physical depletion, and anxiety. As to the personal resilience of lecturer, according to the findings, it is difficult for them to react quickly when anything negative occurs. As a result, efforts to reduce lockdown fatigue among lecturer must focus on developing their coping abilities, which will improve their mental and psychological well-being as well as their general health. A positive psychological intervention or program may be implemented to mitigate the negative effect brought by community lockdown.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The novel coronavirus (NCOV-19) as a global pandemic has caused a drastic effect to the different sectors of the society. With the widespread of the disease, which has caused major socio-economic disruptions, school institutions all over the world have been quick to respond and adapt. Since 2019 when it first emerged in China, the disease has infected over 230 million people worldwide with at least 4.7 million reported deaths [1].

In the Philippines, under the Memorandum from the Executive Secretary, all government agencies are directed to adopt and implement the guidelines on the imposition of "enhanced community quarantine" in the entire Luzon from March 17-April 13, 2020. The memorandum ordered everyone to stay at home and prohibited all physical and social activity outside the home, except frontline and essential workers. Furthermore, schools were shuttered physically in mid-March, 2020 and are still closed as of this writing, following the commission on higher education (CHED) advisory one to eight, with remote teaching and learning settings being developed as a temporary remedy. Hence, beginning in the second semester of academic year 2020-2021, 24 higher education institutions (HEIs) across the country hold restricted face-to-face classes.

In this time of uncertainty and fear, lecturer are one of the most affected individuals. Extended lockdown can result in exhaustion or fatigue to an individual as a result of the disturbances to their daily routines, lack of security, and imminent threat to health. Though fatigue is subjective, it is often an unpleasant feeling in which a person is overcome by an overwhelming sense of tiredness that is not relieved by rest or food intake, an acute need to rest, a lack of physical and mental energy, and a lessened sense of drive and enjoyment [2]. This may be true due to a growing understanding that prolonged stress can lead to burnout in lecturer, which is linked to lower confidence in their ability to do their jobs and a desire to leave the profession [3]. Resilience is negatively associated with indicators of mental ill-health, such as negative affect, depression, and anxiety, as well as positively associated with indicators of mental health, such as positive affect, life satisfaction, subjective well-being, and flourishing [4]. According to certain studies, resilience acts as a mediator between stress and burnout, implying that resilience might reduce the negative effects of stress on burnout [5]. In challenging times, such as pandemics, resilience can lessen the negative impact of stress factors on mental health and promote positive mental health.

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has thrown lecturer into an unpredictable situation. The lockdown has accelerated the shift from traditional to online educational methods. Relationships have been altered by the avoidance of direct contact with others, with implications for their mental health. Also, this pandemic has caused significant stress among lecturer, which was linked to worse mental health, coping, and teaching. It is on this premise that this study was conducted to support the well-being of lecturer in the academe. In this case, negative effects for lecturer, their students, and the educational system as a whole can be avoided.

With the end given the increasing number of COVID-19 confirmed and active cases in the locality and because of the effect of this pandemic on lecturer, this study generally aimed to assess the possibility of lecturer developing fatigue due to lockdown measures of the government. Specifically, the study aimed to: i) determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, marital status, highest educational attainment, annual income, and status of employment; ii) examine the lockdown fatigue of the respondents; iii) determine the extent of agreement on lockdown fatigue of the respondents; iv) determine the extent of agreement on personal resilience of the respondents; v) determine the extent of agreement on coping appraisal of the respondents; and vi) determine the significant difference of the lockdown fatigue, personal resilience and coping appraisal of the respondents when grouped by profile.

Lecturer may experience significant weariness as a result of mandatory lockdown or home confinement measures to slow the spread of COVID-19. The majority of them worry a lot about their personal and family safety during this pandemic, hence, they always see the positive side of the situation. This reflects the coping mindset of the lecturer involved in the study. Male lecturer were found to experience more fatigue than female lecturer. Further, this study provides empirical data that widow or separated lecturer have a higher level of coping appraisal than those of single and married lecturer. This finding highlights the urgent need for marital and gender-specific methods to effectively control the negative effects of the lockdown and prevent weariness. To successfully handle this rising problem among this portion of the population during the coronavirus pandemic, administrators may come up with mental health programs and interventions to manage or reduce lockdown fatigue among lecturer in the university.

Since negative perception towards lockdown fatigue was evident among the teacher-respondents, it is suggested that the cognitive behavioral intervention (CBI) may be employed to reduce the fatigue among the lecturer. The cognitive model is concerned with how we think and how our thoughts affect our mood, bodily responses, and behaviors. The CBI will educate individuals to alter their thoughts, beliefs, and attitudes that are causing depression. This intervention is guided on the principle of associating our positive thoughts with a certain phenomenon.

According to Wright [6], the crafting of the CBI may be anchored to the basic cognitive behavior model (BCBM) which cognitive behavior therapists often employ an integrative multisystem model that conceptualizes patients and organize treatment. This intervention can be utilized by lecturer, special educators, speech-language pathologists, counselors, and psychologists. Social skills, communication, behavior, cognition, coping, and emotional wellbeing/mental health issues can all be addressed using this intervention (e.g., anxiety, depression, anger). Furthermore, once some of these core skills are addressed, effects on adaptive behavior skills may be evident.

Furthermore, the intervention program for lecturer may contain three steps suggested by Sheperd [7]:

STEP 1: become aware of: automatic thoughts, feelings, core beliefs, behaviors, physical reactions and environment.

STEP 2: examination: thoughts are not facts, examine the evidence, look for proof, question and challenge irrational beliefs, and don't believe everything you think.

STEP 3: create alternative thoughts: increase positive self-talk, reduce negative automatic thoughts, and replace irrational beliefs with more rational ones.

As such, in support of the mental health awareness month celebration this October, the researchers intend to facilitate and implement the said intervention to the faculty members of Quirino State University. This initiative as an output of the research study is believed to lessen the lockdown fatigue and can heighten the level of personal resilience and coping appraisal of lecturer in QSU.

Moreover, the conceptual paradigm of the study used the independent variable (IV) and dependent variable (DV) model. Figure 1 depicts the flow of the study. The Independent Variable is consisting of the profile of the respondents such as gender, age, marital status, highest educational attainment, annual income and status of employment. On the other hand, the dependent variable is consisting of lockdown fatigue, personal resilience and coping appraisal of teacher-respondents. Consequently, after taking into consideration the findings and results of the independent and dependent variables, the researcher may propose a mental health program or intervention to address the challenges drawn in the present study. The conceptual framework of the study is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Shows the basic cognitive behavior model (BCBM) as a basis in the crafting the CBI

Figure 2. The conceptual framework of the study

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The descriptive design utilizing online data collection was employed in this study. This is a descriptive study in which information was collected without changing and manipulating the environment. It was used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena to be described like what exists concerning variables or conditions in a situation.

Due to the restrictions causing limited face-to-face interactions brought by the pandemic, the researcher used other platforms in facilitating the structured questionnaire. The Google Form was utilized to gather data from the respondents. The study involved 100 randomly selected faculty members of the university. A four-part questionnaire was used in the study. The first part included items on the teacher-respondents' socio-demographic profiles.

The second part is consisting of items on lockdown fatigue adapted from Labrague & Ballad [8] which evaluates the signs of exhaustion associated with the lockdown or home confinement measures to slow the spread of coronavirus. The third part is consisting of the item on brief resilience scale (BRS) adapted from Smith [9], which determines an individual's ability to bounce back from traumatic or unpleasant events associated with the pandemic and the imposed lockdown measure. Lastly, the fourth part of the questionnaire is consisting of items on coping appraisal adapted from Sheridan [10] which determines the appraisal aspects of coping measure an individual's cognitive and emotional approach to problems. Further, the adapted questionnaire underwent a validity and reliability test to measure its correctness and appropriateness to the context of the study.

In the study, frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents; mean was used to present, analyze, and interpret the data on the lockdown fatigue, personal resilience and coping appraisal; t-test was used to determine the existence of significant differences on the lockdown fatigue, personal resilience and coping appraisal of the respondents when grouped by gender and ANOVA when grouped by gender, marital status, highest educational attainment, annual income, and status of employment.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Socio-demographic profile of the respondents

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the socio demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of gender, age, civil status, highest educational attainment, annual income and status of employment. The table shows that majority of the teacher-respondents are female who belonged to the age bracket of 31-40, married, with ongoing Master's degree, whose Annual Income is PHP240,000.00- PHP478,999.00 and have Permanent positions in the government. Lockdown fatigue of teacher-respondent

Table 1. Profile of the respondents

Profile	f	%
Gender		
Male	22	22.00
Female	78	78.00
Age		
21-30 years old	21	21.00
31-40 years old	44	44.00
41-50 years old	19	19.00
51 years or older	16	16.00
Civil status single	32	32.00
Married	64	64.00
Widow/Separated	4	4.00
Highest educational attainment		
Master's degree (on-going)	30	30.00
Master's degree (graduate)	23	23.00
Doctorate degree (on-going)	19	19.00
Doctorate degree (graduate)	28	28.00
Annual income 48,000-95,999	10	10.00
96,000-143,999	18	18.00
144,000-239,999	25	25.00
240,000-478,999	30	30.00
479,000-718,999	7	7.00
719,000 or higher	10	10.00
Status of appointment permanent	76	76.00
Contract-of-service (COS)	24	24.00
Total	100	100.00

3.2. Personal resilience of the teacher-respondents

Table 2 shows that respondent have higher possibility to recover from the pandemic's traumatic or unpleasant occurrences as reflected with a Grand Mean of 2.36. Resilience is a personal strength that can aid in positive functioning and growth, as well as the prevention of negative emotions, ideas, and actions [11]. Resilience is a personal strength that can lecturer or any individual perform better and develop more effectively by preventing negative emotions, ideas, and actions. In the study of Arslan [12], they considered resilience as a mediator in the link between positive affect, negative affect, and psychological health. They discovered in their study that resilience lowered the impact of negative affect on psychological health while increasing the impact of positive affect. Furthermore, COVID-19-related fear, perceived risk, stress, anxiety, and depression were all significantly mediated by resilience [13].

Table 2. Respondents' extent of agreement on their personal resilience

Statements	Mean	Description
1. I tend to bounce back quickly after hard times.	2.27	Sometimes
2. I have a hard time making it through stressful events.	2.37	Sometimes
3. It is easy for me to recover from a stressful event.	2.37	Sometimes
4. It is hard for me to snap back when something bad happens.	2.39	Sometimes
5. I usually come through difficult times with little trouble.	2.39	Sometimes
Grand Mean	2.36	Sometimes

3.3. Coping appraisal of the teacher-respondents

It can be seen from Table 3 that lecturer use these coping mechanisms sometimes with a Grand Mean of 3.09. During the lockdown caused by the pandemic, lecturer always tries to see the positive side of the situation. According to previous research, changing situation-specific assessments of stress to challenging vs threatening can improve stress responses. The crux is modifying people's attitudes about stress in general could change their cognitive, physiological, and affective stress responses independently of situation-specific judgments. Crum [14] found that a stress-is-enhancing mindset produced sharper increases in anabolic ("growth") hormones relative to a stress-is-debilitating mindset. A stress-is-debilitating mindset under both threat and challenge stress evaluations. When stress was viewed as a challenge, a stress-enhancing mindset resulted in stronger positive affect, increased attentional bias toward positive stimuli, and greater cognitive flexibility, but a stress-debilitating perspective resulted in worse cognitive and affective outcomes.

Coping, according to Kucukalic [15], is a dynamic process that is mutually associated between the individual and his environment. He discovered that those who had been into difficult situations utilized more maladaptive coping strategies than those who had not experienced being troubled. Lecturers deal with stressful situations in a variety of ways. Simple strategies such as a balanced diet, exercise, and appropriate sleep, as well as the ability to recognize work overload and stress-resistant workplaces, are suggested by Sorenson [16]. During this pandemic, people changed their eating habits for the better, even altering their food preferences [17]. Certain coping methods can also be harmful to a person's mental health. Using anger-inducing strategies to relieve stress, such as blaming others and yelling, can lead to mental health issues like insomnia, anxiety, and depression [18]. Hence, the teacher-respondents of the present study handle the situation in a most positive way. The majority see the silver lining of the difficult condition caused by the pandemic.

Table 3. Respondents' extent of agreement on their coping appraisal

Statements	Mean	Description
1. I spend time trying to understand what happened.	3.09	Often
2. I try to see the positive side of the situation.	3.43	Always
3. I try to step back from the problem and think about it from different point of view.	3.11	Often
4. I consider several alternatives for handling the situation.	3.22	Often
5. I try to see the humor in it.	3.00	Often
6. I think about what it might say about bigger lifestyle changes I need to make.	2.97	Often
7. I try to look at the situation that it is not as serious as it seems.	2.80	Often
Grand Mean	3.09	Sometimes

3.4. Significant difference of lockdown fatigue when they are grouped by gender

The Table 4 reveals that there is a significant difference along with the lockdown fatigue statement "I have difficulty concentrating and distracted easily." with a p-value of 0.015. This means that gender influenced their level of agreement on this item. The result conforms to the study of Labrague and Ballad [8] that gender is a significant predictor of lockdown fatigue, with females experiencing more weariness than males.

However, gender differences in the display of sentiments and emotions, such as concern, fear, sadness, and anxiety, as well as in the expression of pain and bodily discomfort, could explain this result. Men tend to suppress their emotions and moods, according to mounting data, whereas women are louder in expressing their emotions [19], [20]. This finding supports a long-held gender stereotype in Philippine culture, according to which women are more comfortable expressing their thoughts, feelings, and emotions than males. Furthermore, during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic, women were more prone than men to suffer from stress disorders, major depression, anxiety, and panic attacks [21], [22]. On the contrary, Nitschke [23] found that gender was not a significant predictor of lockdown fatigue among Australian citizens during the pandemic.

Table 4. T-Test on the agreement of the respondents along with lockdown fatigue when they are grouped by gender

Statements	t	p-value
1. I worry a lot about my personal and family's safety during this pandemic.	1.345	0.186
2. I have felt sad and depressed as a result of the lockdown.	0.812	0.419
3. I frequently felt weak or tired as a result of the lockdown.	0.427	0.670
4. I have difficulty concentrating and distracted easily.	2.485*	0.015
5. I have been feeling irritable.	0.317	0.754
6. I have difficulty falling or staying asleep over thinking about this pandemic.	0.149	0.883
7. I have been losing my interests to do the usual things I love.	-0.081	0.936
8. I have been experiencing a general sense of emptiness.	0.306	0.782
9. I have been experiencing headaches and body pains.	-1.223	0.224
10. I have thoughts that this pandemic will never end soon	0.574	0.567

p-value of .05 or less than is significant

3.5. Significant relationship between coping appraisal and civil status

Table 5 reveals that there is a significant difference along the coping appraisal statement "I spend time trying to understand what happened." with a p-value of 0.031. This means that the civil status of the respondents influenced their level of agreement on this item. According to Flory [24], there are two coping styles that lecturer use, adaptive and maladaptive. Adaptive techniques include obtaining emotional support and using positive reframing, planning, humor, and religion, according to him. On the other hand, self-distraction, denial, substance abuse, behavioral disengagement, and self-blame are examples of maladaptive styles.

This implies that teacher-respondents make use of the adaptive technique to cope with the present situation caused by the global pandemic. Respondents who are widow or separated having experienced adversities of life have a high level of coping appraisal. Lecturer who use more adaptive coping strategies (e.g., relying on social support and exercising self-control) have higher positive affect [25]. Adaptive coping in lecturer, according to research, contributes to enhanced resilience, which leads to higher levels of wellbeing and satisfaction [26], [27]. Self-control, for example, appears to buffer the harmful impacts of negative emotions. Self-control is described as the ability to stop from engaging in undesirable actions that may increase stress [28].

Table 5. Anova on the agreement of the respondents along with coping appraisal when they are grouped by civil status

Statements	F	p-value
1. I spend time trying to understand what happened.	5.192*	0.031
2. I try to see the positive side of the situation.	0.037	0.964
3. I try to step back from the problem and think about it from different point of view.	1.231	0.339
4. I consider several alternatives for handling the situation.	0.177	0.841
5. I try to see the humor in it.	1.683	0.241
6. I think about what it might say about bigger lifestyle changes I need to make.	1.081	0.380
7. I try to look at the situation that it is not as serious as it seems.	2.987	0.103

4. CONCLUSION

Lecturer experienced significant weariness as a result of mandatory lockdown or home confinement measures to slow the spread of COVID-19. Majority of them worry a lot about their personal and family's safety during this pandemic, hence, they always see the positive side of the situation. This reflects the coping

mindset of the lecturer involved in the study. Male lecturer were found to experience more fatigue than female lecturer. Further, this study provides empirical data that widow or separated lecturer have higher level of coping appraisal than those of single and married lecturer. This finding highlights the urgent need for marital and gender-specific methods to effectively control the negative effects of the lockdown and prevent weariness. In order to successfully handle this rising problem among this portion of the population during the corona virus pandemic, administrators may come up with mental health programs and interventions to manage or reduce lockdown fatigue among lecturer in the university.

Since negative perception towards lockdown fatigue was evident among the teacher-respondents, it is suggested that the cognitive behavioral strategy (CBT) may be employed to reduce the fatigue among the lecturer. The cognitive model is concerned with how we think and how our thoughts affect our mood, bodily responses, and behaviors. The CBT educates individuals to alter their thoughts, beliefs, and attitudes that are causing depression. This intervention is guided on the principle of associating our positive thoughts to a certain phenomenon.

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